

Appendix: Methodological toolbox

Tool no. 3_3_2_1	
Title	<p>Stakeholder mapping</p> <p>Definition of case studies, including baseline status, assessment criteria, and socio-ecological goals</p>
Category	Socio-cultural/Environmental/Spatial
Purpose of the method	<p>To evaluate the socio-ecological baseline of diverse coastal systems, analyze challenges such as biodiversity loss, habitat degradation, and governance gaps, and design strategies that promote sustainable management, integrating stakeholder perspectives.</p> <p>This serves as a starting point for easing further research and engagement activities, such as defining Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), developing engagement and governance models, and determining focal actions. By framing the initial scenario, it highlights the relevance of key aspects and identifies critical scenarios that must be considered to ensure effective participatory research and decision-making.</p>
Effort in time	Approximately 6 to 10 months from initial data collection to the completion of baseline analysis and stakeholder consultations.
Number of objects investigated	Ten distinct case study areas, each featuring unique ecosystems, governance structures, and socio-economic conditions.
Data format	Mixed formats including numerical data (e.g., biodiversity indices, habitat quality measures, statistics, indicators), qualitative textual data (e.g., stakeholder interviews, textual responses, stakeholder narratives), geospatial data (e.g., habitat mapping, maps, GIS layers), and visual data (e.g., photos of habitats or biodiversity conditions). Also textual and multimedia data from non-scientific sources such as blogs and social media analysis.
Description	The method involves a structured approach to collecting and integrating socio-ecological data using tools like field surveys, remote sensing, and stakeholder consultations. This process establishes baselines for ecological conditions, economic activities, and governance frameworks, identifying key drivers of change. The analysis employs the Social-Ecological Systems Framework (SESF) to diagnose challenges and guide targeted conservation strategies, ensuring community engagement through participatory workshops and iterative stakeholder feedback.

<p>Basic Literature</p>	<p>Ostrom, E. (2009). "A General Framework for Analyzing Sustainability of Social-Ecological Systems." <i>Science</i>, 325(5939), 419-422.</p> <p>Bio Innovation Service, Directorate-General for Environment (European Commission), Fundación Ibercivis and The Natural History Museum (2018). Citizen science for environmental policy: Development of an EU-wide inventory and analysis of selected practices. Final report for the Directorate-General for Environment (European Commission), EU Publications</p> <p>Partelow, S. (2018). "A Review of the Social-Ecological Systems Framework: Applications, Methods, Modifications, and Challenges." <i>Ecology and Society</i>, 23(4).</p> <p>Fraisl, D., Hager, G., Bedessem, B. et al. Citizen science in environmental and ecological sciences. <i>Nat Rev Methods Primers</i> 2, 64 (2022).</p> <p>PRO-COAST Consortium. (2024). Definition of Case Studies, Including Baseline Status, Assessment Criteria, and Socio-Ecological Goals. D5.1. Horizon Europe.</p>
<p>Contact person within the project</p>	<p>Judith Bielsa Millán Email: bielsa@ibercivis.es Role: Researcher, Ibercivis Foundation.</p>
<p>Linked material</p>	<p>PRO-COAST Deliverable D5.1: https://docs.google.com/document/d/1BN-nC9_ierRGuhznYyQxcmKu62lIH4x/edit?usp=drive_link&oid=101739054819718562908&rtpof=true&sd=true Questionnaires responses from Case Studies: https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1As_OeUs6SmPMZxE65RbD83trBLImp7Qk?usp=drive_link</p>